

EFFECTIVENESS OF APPLYING MODERN METHODS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the demand for learning a foreign language is also increasing day by day, the science of foreign languages is divided into four aspects (reading, reading, listening comprehension and speaking), each of which has its own concept and skills transfer, educational technologies, effective use of modern information technologies in this educational process and other similar topics will be discussed. It also aims to improve the quality and effectiveness of education through the introduction of modern innovative technologies in the educational process.

KEYWORDS

Educational process, similar topics, new technologies, quality, effectiveness, innovative technologies, educational technologies, importance, world community, foreign Languages, opportunities, knowledge, recommendations, new methods, requirements.

INTRODUCTION

After the independence of our country, the interest in teaching foreign languages has grown and many opportunities have been created for young people. As the first President Islam Karimov said, “Currently, great importance is attached to the teaching of foreign languages in our country. This, of course, is not in vain. There is no need to underestimate the importance of perfect knowledge of foreign languages for our countries, which today are striving to take their rightful place in the world community, for our people, who are building their great future in cooperation with our foreign partners”. As a logical continuation of these ideas, the Presidential Decree of December 10, 2012 “On Measures to Further Improve the System of Teaching Foreign Languages” expanded the opportunities for learning foreign languages.

New methods and requirements for foreign language teaching in the country have been developed in accordance with the Recommendations of the European Framework for Assessment of Knowledge and Skills of Foreign Language Teachers

(CEFR). According to him, textbooks have been created for students of secondary schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms are equipped with stands and new information and communication technologies. The demand for learning a foreign language is growing day by day. Foreign language science is divided into four aspects (reading, reading, listening comprehension, and speaking), each of which provides specific concepts and skills. Educational technology is the effective use of modern information technology in the educational process. It also aims to improve the quality and effectiveness of education through the introduction of modern innovative technologies in the educational process.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

In particular, there are several advantages to using such information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language. The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is invaluable. The use of technology is useful in every aspect of learning a foreign language (reading, reading, listening and speaking). For example, to listen and understand, of course, it is impossible to do this process without a computer, player, CD. Listening is one of the most important parts of language learning. This requires the student to pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation, grammatical rules, vocabulary, and meanings at the same time. An important factor in the use of modern technologies in education is the ability of students to know and use information and communication technologies. Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technology is one of the most effective ways.

In the process, including:

- When using computers, the student can watch and listen to foreign language videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons;
- It is possible to listen and watch foreign language radio broadcasts and television programs;
- The use of tape recorders and cassettes, which are more traditional methods; □
CD players are available.

The use of these tools will make the process of learning a foreign language more interesting and effective. Today, interactive games are becoming a tradition in schools. It is well known that a variety of games help students demonstrate their abilities, focus, increase their knowledge and skills, and become stronger. The basis of the use of game technology is the activity that activates and accelerates the student. According to psychologists, the psychological mechanisms of playful activity are based on the fundamental needs of the individual to express themselves, to find a stable place in life, to selfmanage, to realize their potential.

At the heart of any game should be the generally accepted principles and tactics of education. Learning games should be based on the subjects. During the games, the student is more interested in this activity than in a normal lesson and works more comfortably. It should be noted that the game is, first of all, a way of teaching. Students take an active part in playful lessons, strive to win, and through them the teacher educates the student. The student is interested in believing that he or she can play, speak, listen, understand, and write in English.

We know that in the current educational process, the student must be a subject. Focusing on more interactive methods will increase the effectiveness of education. One of the most important requirements for English lessons is to teach students to think independently. Today, English language teachers use the following innovative methods based on the experience of teachers in the United States and the United Kingdom:

- “Creative Problem Solving” - to use this method, the beginning of the story is read and the end is given to the students;

- “Merry Riddles” - Teaching riddles to students is important in teaching English, they learn words they are unfamiliar with and find the answer to a riddle;

- “Quick answers” help to increase the effectiveness of the lesson;

- “Warm-up exercises” - use a variety of games in the classroom to engage students in the lesson;

- “Pantomime” is a method that can be used in a class where very difficult topics need to be explained, or when students are tired of writing exercises.; “A chain story” method helps to develop students’ oral skills;

- “Acting characters” - this method can be used in all types of lessons. Professionals such as Interpreter, Translator, Writer, and Poet can participate in the course and talk to students.;

- “Thinkers meeting” - poets and writers such as W. Shakespeare, A. Navoi, R. Burns can be “invited”. At such times, using the wise words they say in class will help young people to become perfect human beings;

- When pictures speak is a very convenient method that helps to teach English and develop students’ oral speech by using thematic pictures;

- “Quiz cards” - cards are distributed according to the number of students and allow all students to attend classes at the same time, which saves time.

As we have seen, each innovative technology has its own set of advantages. All of these methods involve collaboration between teacher and student, active participation of the student in the educational process. In short, the use of innovative methods in English lessons develops students’ logical thinking skills, fluency, and the ability to respond quickly and accurately. Such methods stimulate the student’s interest

in knowledge. The student strives to prepare well for the lessons. This makes students active participants in the learning process. As the education system sets itself the task of nurturing a free-thinking, wellrounded, mature person, in the future we, future teachers, will contribute to the more perfect development of ways to effectively use innovative technologies are possible.

Knowledge of events is taught in theory. Knowledge of languages, especially multilingualism, is of great importance in today's world of international relations. Pupils and students studying in our country usually learn three languages. These languages are referred to by special names. These are: native language, second language, and foreign language. Mother tongue is the first language that plays a special role in the formation of thinking. When it comes to the second language, it is considered as the language of brothers and sisters of other nationalities, neighbors.

The main goal of the system of continuing education is to train highly spiritual, competitive and intellectually gifted specialists. Following the implementation of this decision, the process of applying modern pedagogical technologies in the education system has become widespread. Today, scientific and technological progress requires the introduction of new modern technologies in all areas, including education. Therefore, the National Program of Personnel Training emphasizes the need to provide the educational process with advanced pedagogical technologies, and new models of education are being created.

The demand for learning foreign languages has become a necessity at the same time. Changes in the socio-economic spheres of the country, rapid development require the introduction of new pedagogical technologies in the educational process, the need to find and apply modern methods of language teaching in the educational process. Leading scientists, Methodists search for modern pedagogical technologies, methods and techniques of foreign language teaching.

The advantage of teaching a foreign language on the basis of pedagogical technology over previous methods is, firstly, that it considers the educational process as a whole, the purpose of education, its content, teaching methods and tools to design the stages of education, control the educational process and in the design of its project, bringing its components, such as the evaluation of learning outcomes, into an interdependent system. Second, it is not about students memorizing the knowledge they have been given, but about doing practical work at the end of the teaching and learning process. The introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies in foreign language lessons, their integration into the content of education, the discovery of new ways of teaching will create the basis for meeting the requirements of state educational standards. In order to make the lesson comfortable and lively for the teacher, it is

necessary to develop a variety of visual aids and use them in a timely manner and in the classroom, using modern advanced pedagogical technologies. “Brainstorming”, “Cluster”, “Working with red and green cards”, “BBB (I know. I want to know. I learned.)”, “Lily of the Valley” and “Pin board” methods are among them.

The main components of teaching a foreign language in practical training are the integrated integration of listening comprehension, speaking, reading and writing. From the earliest stages of teaching any foreign language, it is recommended that learners be given small dialogues, grammar games, phrases that are necessary in everyday life. These methods increase the interest of learners in the language. Then the themes, the methods, the technologies change and become more complex. In this case, the widespread use of games such as debates, interviews, competitions develops the learner’s free, independent, logical thinking, prepares learners for free communication and dialogue. This is an effective way to develop learners’ thinking, reasoning, and reasoning skills. Of course, practical exercises play an important role in the solid and perfect learning of foreign languages.

The teacher must clearly define the education and upbringing in accordance with the order of the state educational standard, and at the same time carry out the didactic goal with pedagogical skills. To do this, it is necessary to ensure the connection between disciplines on the basis of new and modern pedagogical technologies. It is also important to properly manage student activities, use time efficiently, to direct students to useful activities in the classroom and outside the classroom, to give them the opportunity to develop their free and creative thinking skills, to learn foreign languages with enthusiasm. is a necessary factor in ensuring learning and their activity. Student activism refers to a range of issues, such as creativity and independent thinking. In the process of new pedagogical technology, the quality and effectiveness of teaching will be positive if the following work is done:

1. Assign homework normally and choose topics that the student is interested in and loves;
2. Discuss the assignments with the class, filling in and reviewing strengths and weaknesses;
3. Formation of duties and responsibilities in the student;
4. Linking knowledge with practical work, teaching creative activity;
5. Build a sense of national pride and friendship;
6. Formation of computer literacy;
7. Extensive use of handouts, visual aids, modern methods and techniques in foreign language lessons.

At the present time, in all higher education institutions, including higher education institutions, modern information technologies, multimedia complexes, Modern textbooks and manuals based on interactive methods, audiovideo methodical manuals are provided with the necessary teaching aids, visual aids, modern computer sets, electronic and interactive whiteboards. This will increase the interest in the world of science, especially the ways to expand knowledge and skills in foreign languages. The peculiarity of pedagogical technology is that it designs and implements the learning process that ensures the achievement of learning objectives. The Pinboard method can also be used to increase the effectiveness of the lesson. The word “pinboard” is derived from the English word “pin”- “strengthen” means “board”. The essence of this teaching method is that the discussion and learning dialogue are connected in a practical way. Its strengths are its developmental and nurturing function. Students develop a culture of communication and debate, the ability to express their opinions not only orally but also in writing, and the ability to think logically and systematically. In addition, we can use the following methods and techniques to increase the effectiveness of lessons:

1. Debates: study groups are divided into two groups in the form of discussions on a topic.
2. Ice breaker: Aimed at removing barriers between educators and learners. Games: Business or roleplaying games. Only in this game, instead of textual materials, a real-life situation is played in which students play a role.
3. Working with books: this method is aimed at the ability of students to independently master the learning materials, self-examination skills, to consciously express the content of the given text.
4. Individual (practical method). Students focus their knowledge on practical tasks.
5. Conversation: These are dialogic, question-and-answer methods of teaching and learning. Interviews can be individual or group.
6. Teaching others: In this way, learners teach each other information and data on the problem at hand.
7. Roundtable - Students sit at a roundtable and write answers to each other's questions in an envelope.

Currently, in Uzbekistan the demand for learning and teaching foreign languages is growing. The fulfillment of these tasks by young people will accelerate the integration of our society into the world community, develop economic and cultural ties between the countries. The National Training Program and the Law on Education provide for the introduction and mastery of modern pedagogical technologies in foreign language teaching. The effectiveness of the course depends largely on the pedagogical technologies used in the learning process. The effective use of modern

pedagogical technologies in foreign language teaching increases the interest of students in the language and ensures that their knowledge, skills and abilities in the language are high. According to the form of modern pedagogical technology is free education, non-traditional training and activation, research by method, problem solving, independent creative free thinking. Application of modern pedagogical technologies in foreign language teaching is:

1. The use of direct distance learning with the help of computer technology (Internet) in the teaching of foreign languages;
2. Organization of group and completed work of students and computer control (implementation of test tasks by computer);
3. Use of technical means (audiotape, video);
4. It consists of the use of visual aids (thematic drawings, diagrams).

The modern lesson must be intense in an aggressive spirit. The teacher has to keep up with the lesson, keep up with the times, and even earlier. If he organizes a lesson in the spirit of the times, in accordance with the requirements of the time, the lesson will inevitably be modern and full of innovations.

The use of computer technology, modern information technology in the educational process in the implementation of the above requirements opens the door to opportunities for students to consistently master the program materials and apply the acquired knowledge in practice.

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CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the benefits of modern innovative educational technologies are the development of students' cognitive activity, educating them in all respects, increasing their interest in subsequent topics. The introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies in foreign language lessons, its introduction into the educational process, the discovery of new ways of teaching will lay the foundation for meeting the requirements of state educational standards. Therefore, every educator must use modern pedagogical technologies to improve the quality of lessons, to develop it, and to contribute to the goal of raising our education system to the level of world education.

REFERENCES

1. Kavilova, T. (2020). Modern methods of teaching a foreign language. Archive of Scientific Publications JSPI.
2. Voronova, E. N. (2014). Modern technologies and methods of teaching foreign language in higher educational institution. Perspectives of Science & Education, 7(1).
3. Boychayeva, D. R., Rahmanova, D. A., & Yuldasheva, M. B. (2019). Modern methods of teaching foreign languages to the university. International Journal on Integrated Education, 2(6), 18-20.
4. Muratova, G., & Abraimova, N. (2020). THE USE OF INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES AND MODERN METHODS IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE. Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal, 2020(2), 175-182.
5. Kavilova, T. (2020). Actual problems of teaching a foreign language. Archive of Scientific Publications JSPI.
6. Khoshimova, D., Otajonova, D., & Khaldarchayeva, G. (2020). Modern Technologies in Teaching Foreign Languages. Academic Research in Educational Sciences, (3).
7. Zhabo, N., Avdonina, M., Krivosheeva, E., Likhacheva, I., & Meer, T. (2017, October). Modern methods of teaching foreign languages for specific purposes. In Conference proceedings. ICT for language learning. *libreriauniversitaria. it Edizioni* (p. 288).
8. Ismailova, K. E., Beloglazova, L. B., & Bondareva, O. V. (2018). Modern methods of teaching Russian as a foreign language to non-philology students. *Man in India*, 97(14), 1-15.

9. Chernysh, V. V., & Vaseiko, Y. (2020). Modern Methods of Training Foreign Language Teachers. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 9(7), 332-344.
10. Djurayeva, Y., Orazova, F., & Kayumova, G. (2020). Applying independent education in foreign language classes and its problems. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*, 8(10), 195-199.
11. Solomatina, A. G., & Saenko, E. S. (2018). Innovative methods of learning foreign language. In *CURRENT PROBLEMS OF AGRICULTURAL SCIENCE, PRODUCTION AND EDUCATION* (pp. 339-344).
12. Kazakbaev, A. (2020). THE PROBLEMS AND METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. *The Light of Islam*, 2020(2), 51-60.
13. Yelahina, N. I., Fedchyshyn, N. O., Klishch, H. I., & Horpinich, T. I. (2019). Effective methods in foreign language teaching of medical students. *Medical education*, (1), 48-54.
14. Belyaeva, I. G., Samorodova, E. A., Voron, O. V., & Zakirova, E. S. (2019). Analysis of innovative methods' effectiveness in teaching foreign languages for special purposes used for the formation of future specialists' professional competencies. *Education sciences*, 9(3), 171.
15. Shumskyi, O. (2016). Modern approaches to foreign language teaching: world experience. *Equitable professional pedagogy*, (6 (1)), 41-46.
16. Bakirova, H. B. (2020). TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE TERMINOLOGY AT A NON LANGUAGE UNIVERSITIES. *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL JOURNAL "INNOVATION TECHNICAL AND TECHNOLOGY"*, 1(2), 46-50.
17. Maiier, N., & Ustyomenko, O. (2018). Modern methods and technologies for developing pre-service foreign language and culture teachers' methodological competence. *Advanced education*, (10), 12-20.
18. Ahmad, I. (2014). Effective and modern methods of teaching a foreign language in high school. *Theoretical nutrition of culture, education and culture*, (50), 31-33.
19. Mardievna, B. M., Mukhamadjanovna, J. S., Nematovich, N. O., & Azamovich, T. V. (2020). The importance of modern methods and technologies in learning English. *Journal of critical reviews*, 7(6), 143-148.
20. Болибекова, М. М. (2012). О свойствах форм сказуемого и их передача на английский язык. *Вестник Южно-Уральского государственного гуманитарно-педагогического университета*, (2).
21. Болибекова, М. (2013). О свойствах форм категории сказуемости (на примере узбекского и английского языков). In *Новое в науке* (pp. 31-35)ll